

MINI-SONAR---A MINIATURIZED SECTOR SCANNING SONAR

Jack E. Holzschuh

Naval Ocean Systems Center
P.O. Box 997
Kailua, Hawaii 96734

ABSTRACT

Use of small submersibles has increased in recent years. A vehicle that is simply a swimming TV camera can be made quite small, but its utility is limited because of its limited view of its surroundings. The mini-sonar program was started at NOSC to develop a small sector scanning sonar for use on small vehicles without affecting their bulk.

A scan-within-a-pulse type sonar was selected. Design range is 100 yards, operating frequency 300kHz, sector 80° , beamwidth 4° , and size 9 x 5 x 4 inches. An added constraint is use of pressure tolerant electronics.

The largest contributing factor to meeting all these design requirements was a unique beamformer. This beamformer uses sine and cosine weighted resistors rather than a delay and sum technique. Also, by electrically switching the receiving array end for end, the required number of beamformers is halved.

This paper discusses the design of this sonar, concentrating on the beamformer.

I. INTRODUCTION

The objective in building the Mini-Sonar (MS) was to make available an obstacle avoidance scanning sonar that could be used on small (less than 300 lbs air weight) submersibles. The technical objectives included a range of 100m, beamwidth of 4° horizontal and 20° vertical, sector width of 80° , range resolution of 0.4m, receiving sensitivity of +60db re 1 Pa, depth capability to 6500m and size of 10cm X 13cm X 25cm. Section II, Description of Mini-Sonar, provides more detailed information.

The rest of the paper details the approach to meeting the objectives. Section III, Background, discusses the overall design philosophy of the sonar and briefly describes some of the ideas and designs tried and rejected. Section IV, Beamformer, discusses the unique part of the sonar, the

resistive beamformer. Section V describes testing of MS and Section VI, Status, describes MS today.

II. DESCRIPTION OF MINI-SONAR

Mini-sonar is a scan-within-a-pulse obstacle avoidance sonar. Its primary function is active echo ranging with a secondary function of passive listening. Its design range is 100m, operating frequency is 300kHz and pulse duration is 0.5×10^{-3} sec at a source level of +186 dB re μ Pa at 1m. The receiving array has 26 elements spaced at one half wavelength for a total active length of 7cm. Receiving beamwidth at broadside is 4° . Total scan sector is 80° divided into 10 beams on either side of center. Its range resolution is 38cm.

The soundhead, a 10cm X 13cm X 25cm package, contains all the subsurface electronics. These include pre-amps, beamformers, timing and synchronizing circuits, scanner, demodulator, power amplifier and line driver. The soundhead supplies the topside electronics with the scanned, demodulated sonar output plus timing and synchronizing pulses for the display.

The topside electronics consist of the sonar control console, scan generator and display. The control console has three selectable ranges, 25m, 50m, and 100m, an on-off switch, and a level control for the transmit power. Sonar information is displayed in a PPI format on a commercial CRT display. The timing and synchronizing pulses from the soundhead are used to generate the X and Y deflection voltages in the topside scan generator. The processed information from the acoustic returns is used to modulate the intensity of the display (Z axis). Thus, the operator is presented a display that is pie-shaped, the point corresponding to the front of the vehicle, with obstacles displayed as bright spots within a pie-shaped sector ahead of the vehicle.

III. BACKGROUND

As originally envisioned, the MS was to be used on the NOSC Snoopy vehicle. Snoopy is basically a swimming TV camera and is used for underwater visual inspection tasks of many sorts. One of the

IV. BEAMFORMER

problems with Snoopy, however, was its very limited visual range. It was felt that a small scanning sonar would add significantly to the utility of the vehicle. As all scanning sonars on the market at that time were heavier than Snoopy itself, an IED program was initiated at NOSC to fabricate a scanning sonar that was usable on Snoopy and other similar sized vehicles.

The design philosophy that evolved in meeting this goal included the following considerations; (1) use of linear receiving array, (2) use of pressure tolerant electronics to eliminate pressure vessels, (3) design for hybridization, and (4) complete sonar packaged in single container of size noted in Introduction. The primary purpose of each of these considerations was minimization of the size of the sonar.

The consequence of the first consideration was a slight increase in the beamwidth at the extremes of the scan. The consequence of the second consideration was the requirement to carefully select all components to be pressure tolerant. It was felt enough information was available on this technology to assure success of a totally pressure tolerant sonar. The consequences of the last two considerations were a requirement for careful, yet clever design and packaging of the sonar sub-systems.

The pre-amp subsystem was designed using a well proven IC amplifier, the MC 1350. This IC, or its metal packaged equivalent, has been used successfully in similar applications. The plastic packaged configuration was used because of the pressure tolerant requirement. Matching of input impedances and output impedances for the required gain and derivation of the time varying gain voltage were all straightforward design procedures.

Design of the beamformer section is where the most effort was expended and most problems were encountered. A RLC delay line preformed beam beamformer was rejected because of size and the fact that it does not lend itself to hybridization, the ultimate goal for the MS electronics. The first design attempted was a RC phase shift and add scanner. This design proved unusable for several reasons. First, either R or C had to be varied for the scanner to scan. The only component that could meet all requirements for a variable R was a field effect transistor. These proved to be very difficult to match in terms of input control voltage vs resistance. Next a varying C with a voltage variable capacitor was tried, however, problems with driving 26 of these at the required scanning speed proved formidable. The scanner also suffered because it was a series type phase shift-adder, thus, if any one of the circuit components failed, the whole scanner failed.

Next, a resistive type beamformer, pre-formed beams and beam scanning was tried. This technique is the one selected for the MS and discussed in the next section.

The reasons for selection of the resistive beamformer seem very logical and reasonable when viewed in light of the background information. It uses components that have a good history of operation as pressure tolerant components, that are easily adapted to hybridization and that are readily available and inexpensive. The only problem is actual design of the beamformer. This design is detailed below.

The general equation for the phase shift at any element n about the center of a linear array with half wavelength element spacing and an arrival angle θ is:

$$\theta_n = \frac{(2n-1) \pi \sin \theta}{2}$$

for the right half (with an even number of elements), and

$$\theta_{-n} = \frac{(1-2n) \pi \sin \theta}{2}$$

for the left half of the elements (Figure 1).

FIGURE 1. LINE ARRAY

Let us now define a weighting function as the normalized output of each element at the instant the wavefront passes through the center of the array. This weighting function is determined for a given sound arrival angle ψ and is the function that gives maximum output for arrivals from that angle and no other. The expression for that weighting function is:

$$W_R = \cos \frac{(2n-1) \pi \sin \psi}{2}$$

for the right half of the array, and

$$W_L = \cos \frac{(1-2n) \pi \sin \psi}{2}$$

for the left half.

A FORTRAN program was written that multiplies the weighting functions times the normalized element outputs and sums the product for 26 elements. The output of this program is shown in Figure 2. As expected, the output is symmetrical about the center of the array.

Figure 2. Plot of weighting function times normalized element output for $\theta = 0$ to 50° , $\psi = 12^\circ$, 26 elements

The problem now is to eliminate the output on the "undesirable" side and enhance the output on the "desirable" side. This may be done simply by noting that the original weighting function is an even function and therefore generated an even function. If we use an odd weighting function of the same magnitude, generate another sum of products and add to the first sum of products, this should give the desired output. The required odd weighting functions are:

$$V_R = \sin \frac{(2n-1) \pi \sin \psi}{2}$$

For the right side, and

$$V_L = \sin \frac{(1-2n) \pi \sin \psi}{2}$$

for the left.

Again, a FORTRAN program was written to include necessary multiplying, summing, squaring and square rooting. The output of this program is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Plot of sum of even and odd weighting functions times normalized element output. $\theta = 0^\circ$ to 50° , $\psi = 20^\circ$, 26 elements

The results of the computer modeling proved analytically that a resistive beamformer could be built and would meet all design goals and philosophies. The next step in the evolution of MS was the design, fabrication and testing of this beamformer.

Design was quite straightforward. Determine the value of the weighting resistors for the sine and cosine weighted summers then sum the outputs of these two (diagram of this circuit is shown in Figure 4). The only design problem was keeping the summing amps symmetrical, as some of the weighting resistors go into the inverting input and some into the non-inverting input. A computer program was written that calculated the values of the weighting resistor as well as the value of the balancing resistor required for symmetry of the summing amp.

Figure 4. Diagram of resistive beamformer

Normally, in a preformed beam type sonar, one beamformer is used per beam. In the case of MS, this implies that 20 beamformers are required. However, by putting in a set of switches behind the pre-amplifiers and in front of the beamformers, the array may be electrically switched end for end. This switching eliminated the requirement for 20 beamformers because the same beamformers can be used for both the left and the right beams. Thus only 11 instead of 20 beamformers are required. CMOS switches proved to be satisfactory for the switching job. Figure 5 shows a diagram of the switch input-output.

Figure 5. End for end electrical switching of array

V. TESTING

In order to test the resistive beamformer concept, a prototype of the MS was built. This prototype contained all required circuitry but only the pre-amps and switches were in the soundhead. The rest of the electronics were fabricated on two-sided printed circuit boards and housed in an open chassis.

The first series of beamformer tests were to determine beamwidth and relative response of each of the beams. For these tests, a projector was suspended in front of the soundhead and its angle was varied with respect to the receiving array. The results of this test for the 0° , 12° , and 33° beams are shown in Figure 6. Here, the beams appear to be more than 4° wide, especially the broadside beam. Additionally, the relative amplitude decreases with increasing beam angle. The fact that beams were formed and at the proper angles was gratifying at this point.

Figure 6. Beamwidth and response of 0° , 12° and 33° beams

The next test was with the sonar actively transmitting against a target. The target used was a 14 inch triplane. The beam outputs of 0° , 20° and 33° are shown in Figures 7, 8 and 9. Again, the amplitude is reduced at large beam angles.

Figure 7. Beam response for target at 0°

Figure 8. Beam response for target at 20°

Figure 9. Beam response for target at 33°

This reduction in amplitude at the higher beam angles implied a pronounced directivity of the receiving elements. Though the elements were designed to be non-directional out to at least 40° , it appeared that this design objective was not met. A directivity test on several of the individual elements in the array was subsequently run. The results are shown in Figure 10. As suspected, the elements do show pronounced directivity at angles less than 40° . This directivity can account for both the reduced amplitude response at large beam angles and the degraded beamwidths of all the beams.

Figure 10. Element response patterns

VI. PRESENT STATUS OF MINI-SONAR

During the testing phase described briefly earlier, the operation of MS was confirmed, though all design objectives were not fully satisfied. A decision had to be made at that point whether to go through another design cycle, especially on the receiver transducer assembly, or accept the MS with less than perfect performance. The decision was made not to go through a redesign and refabrication of the receiver. Additionally, another vehicle called FOCUS (Fiber Optic Controlled Underwater Stereo) was in the final stages of fabrication as MS testing was completed and MS became operational. Thus, it was decided to install the MS on the FOCUS vehicle.

The FOCUS vehicle was designed to be a test bed vehicle for an underwater stereo TV viewing system. The vehicle is approximately 1m X 2m x 1m and weighs approximately 530kg. The reason it is so heavy is that it carries all its power as lead acid batteries. Its only link to the surface is through a single optical fiber. All the command and control information comes down this fiber and both TV videos (for stereo) are sent up on it.

When the sonar is operating, it uses one of the TV channels as its uplink. The sonar does not require this large bandwidth, it was done that way for multiplexing expedience. To date only pool tests have been run on the vehicle, however the sonar has operated satisfactorily.

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